

MODIFICATION OF CONSONANTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article discusses the distinctive features of English consonant sounds and their classification comparing with Uzbek phonemes. Usually the distinction between a vowel and a consonant is regarded to be not phonetic, but phonemic. From the phonetic point of view the distinction between a vowel and a consonant is based on their articulatory – acoustic characteristics, i. e. a vowel is produced as a pure musical tone without any obstruction of air-stream in the speech tract. There are other criteria to distinguish a vowel from a consonant as well.

Keywords: sounds, articulation, distinction, category, consonant, pronunciation.

INTRODUCTION

Most of phonological theories in USA are based on the method of distribution of sounds in the linear of speech. They analyse syntagmatic relations between the elements of speech. This is also one of the possible ways of categorization of linguistic elements [5].

In spite of all these contradictions we should use traditional distinction between vocoid- contoid in the phonetic sense and vowel-consonant for the linguistic categories. The phonemes system of the English language consists of vowel phonemes and consonant phonemes. Usually the pronunciation of vowels depends on the neighbouring consonants. Therefore we should begin the description of the phonemic system of English with consonants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to place of articulation the consonants may be labial and pharyngeal (/h/). Labial consonants are divided into bilabial (as English /p/, /b/, /m/, /w/) and labio-dental (English /f/, /v/). The lingual consonants may be fore lingual (English /t/, /d/, /s/, /z/, /l/, /n/, /ʃ/, /ʒ/, /tʃ/, /dʒ/), interlingual and backlingual (/k/, /g/, /ŋ/) [2].

The chief points of obstruction at the place of articulation, besides labial (bilabial and labio-dental), are dental (allophones of the phonemes /t/, /d/, etc.), alveolar (/t/, /d/, /s/, /z/, /l/), retroflex (G.A./r/), cacuminal (GB /r/), palato-alveolar /ʃ/, /ʒ/, /tʃ/, /dʒ/, palatal /j/, velar /k/, /g/, /ŋ/ uvular (Scottish /E/), glottal /ʔ/ - stop which is used more often in GA and in some English dialects). All these characterize the place of obstruction formed at some points of speech organs [1].

The manner of articulation makes it possible to distinguish occlusive (/p, b, t, d, k, g/), constrictive (/f, v, s, z, θ, ð, ʃ, ʒ/) consonants and affricates (/tʃ, dʒ/). In turn, occlusive consonants may be two types: plosives or stops, in the production of which noise is essential and sonorant's or sonorant's /m, n, ŋ/. In the production of which tone prevails over noise. Constrictive consonants may be divided into fricatives and sonorant's. Fricative consonants may be unicentral (those in which narrowing has two foci) and bicentral (produced by two foci narrowing as in /f, ʒ/). Unicentral consonants may be produced either with a flat narrowing (/f, v, θ, ð, h/) or at round narrowing (as in English /s, z/). As to constrictive sonorant's, then may be medial (as in English /w, v, j/) and lateral (/l/) [4].

The next class of consonants namely affricates are formed by the stream of air stopped first (as in the production of plosives) and then the closure is released with friction (as in fricatives). Sometimes these type of sounds are called **accsive** – constrictive or plosive – fricative complexes as the English /tʃ, dʒ/. Affricates may also be unicentral. (as the Russian and Uzbek **ac** /ɯ/) and bicentral (as in the English /tʃ, dʒ/).

The rolled (or thrilled) sonant's are not characteristic for GB and GA but may be heard in some positions, especially when /r/ precedes /t/ and /d/ it drops its sonorar feature [3]. Therolled sonant's are found in Russian (/p/) and Uzbek (/p/).

The next principle of the classification of consonants is based on the presence or absence of voice, according to which voiced and voiceless consonants may be distinguished. This distinction is closely connected by the degree of breath and muscular effort, involved in the articulation. Usually the English voiced consonants are articulated by relatively weak energy of the speech organs, whereas the voiceless consonants are pronounced by relatively strong energy. This distinction, indicated by the feature fortis-lenis (from latin words which mean "tense-lax"), is very important phonologically. There are eight pairs of voiceless – voiced, resp. fortis – lenis consonants in English: /p–b/, /t–d/, /f–v/, /s–z/, / tʃ- dʒ /, / θ-ð /, / tʃ- dʒ /, /k–g/ [2].

The position of the soft palate is very important in the production of consonants. When the soft palate takes a high position it blocks the air-passage into the nasal cavity and the air passes through the mouth cavity. The consonants produced are called orals (/p, t, s, z/ etc.). When the soft palate is lowered, the vibrating breath passes through the nose. The nasal cavity, along with the oral cavity or part of it, function as a resonance chamber (as in /m, n, ŋ/). The general principles of the consonant classification explained here are outlined in the comparative table of English and Uzbek consonant phonemes given below [3].

In comparing the consonant systems of two languages, it is suitable to begin with the inventories of phonemes set up in both languages. The inventory of the English consonant phonemes comprises the following 25 phonemes: /p/, /b/, /t/, /s/, /k/, /g/, /n/, /ŋ/, /l/, /m/, /h/, /v/, /d/, /z/, /f/, /ʒ/, /tʃ/, /dʒ/, /w/, /r/, /tʃ/, /θ/, /ð/, /f/ and the facultative or optinal phoneme /M/.

The inventory of the Uzbek consonants also consists of 25 phonemes /n/, /б/, /ф/, /в/, /с/, /з/, /т/, /д/, /ш/, /ж/, /к/, /г/, /х/, /ғ/, /қ/, /х/:, /н/, /л/, /р/, /й/, /тш/, -/ч/, /дж/-/ж/, /м/, /нг/, /тс/ц//:

Some of the English consonants, for example, / ə,ð,m/ can not be found in Uzbek. Likewise, the Uzbek consonants /x, ғ, қ, тс /ц/ do not exist in English. We can *arrogate* the differences in the inventives of consonant phonemes of both languages into a single table. As we look at the table of consonants we find differences in the number and articulation of some consonants. For example, the Uzbek consonants /т,д/ are articulated in a more formal- position, being dental and dorsal, than the English consonants /t,d/, which have an alveolar and apical articulation. The Uzbek plosive (stop) uvular /қ/ does not exist in English. It is articulated in a more backward position than the backlingual consonants.

It is possible to compare the acoustic distinctive features of the English and Uzbek consonant phonemes. We can notice in the table that sharp/ plain (non-sharp) feature is typical of Uzbek vowels, as they may be used after palatal or non-palatal consonants in which their quality may be changed.

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